

Chitosan and its Significant Properties: A Review

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Abstract: Chitin a precursor to chitosan is the penultimate versatile polymer thereafter the β -linked sugar polymer; they are reflective sugars, reactive and with non-brittle properties present in the cellular walls of fungi and in the shells of crustaceans and other insects. Chitosan and their formulations are non toxic to human and biotic surroundings (GRAS) with good characteristics such adaptability and blendable, non-toxicity and financially effective. The properties of this amine linked biocomposite expose their numerous biotechnological applications as enlisted. Search for renewability of their supply is a biotechnological topnotch to meet with their over-rising demand in the today global market.

Keywords: chitin, chitosan, amine, biocomposite, properties.

Background of the Study

The amino sugar linked polymer is a naturally existing unbranched sugar compounds of composites of β -(1,4)-linked glucosamine units (2-amino-2-deoxy- β -d-glucopyranose) together with some repeating proportions of *N*-acetylglucosamine units (2-acetamino-2-deoxy- β -d-glucopyranose) (Milosavic *et al.*, 2005). Chitosan is the most abundant cationic ($-\text{NH}_2$) biopolymer in existence. Because the amino groups in chitosan are protonated (H^+), it dissolves in diluted solutions of organic and inorganic acids ($\text{pH} < 6$). Because of its polycationic nature, it can combine with polyanions to form polyelectrolyte complexes (Bobu *et al.*, 2011). It has excellent film forming ability and can also be prepared in films, fibers, hydrogels and micro/nanoparticles (Chang *et al.*, 2011). The polar hydroxyl and amino reactive groups of the compounds permit the vast applicability of the different

formulations of the based compounds. Chitin a precursor to chitosan is the penultimate versatile polymer thereafter the β -linked sugar polymer; they are reflective sugars, reactive and with non-brittle properties present in the cellular walls of fungi and in the shells of crustaceans and other insects (Korma *et al.*, 2018). Chitosan and their formulations are non toxic to human and biotic surroundings (GRAS) with good characteristics such adaptability and blendable, non-toxicity and financially effective (Thanou *et al.*, 2001). Chitosan are ecological friendly with high molecular weight and similarity to cellulose (Korma *et al.*, 2018). Increasingly demand on chitosan commercially as suitable resource material due to their unique features including biocompatibility, biodegradability, adsorption, and ability to form films, and to chelate metal ions in waste water composites (Trombotto *et al.*, 2008).

Fig 1. Structure of cellulose, chitin and chitosan (Korma *et al.*, 2018).

Sources, production and characterization of chitosan

Chitosan which is a derivative of chitin is widely seen in certain organisms and sea animals; their abundance in these animals is made manifest by the percentage composition of chitin in these animals (Davis, 2011). Various insects such as wing termites, soldier ants while filamentous fungi of *Zygomycete* and *Deutromycete* family are said to have these biopolymers in abundance. Sea animal of crustacea family (crab, snails, periwinkle, prawns etc) are implicated sources of chitosans (Korma *et al.*, 2018).

Production and purification of chitosan from biopolymers composites comprises of cascade of experimental steps generally divided into two major groups:

- a. Chemical steps
- b. Enzymatic steps

The chemical steps

The chemical procedures can be further alkali and acid based treatment methods. These treatments are basically grouped under the following: Demineralization with 1M HCl, Deproteinization with one molar (1M) caustic soda, Depigmentation with 1% depigmenting agents such as hypochlorites, alcohols, acetones, acidified permanganates etc and Deacetylation of the produced chitin to form chitosan using 40% caustic soda (Krishnaveni and Raganathan, 2009). Chitin is extracted from fungi in a manner akin to that of crustaceans and other ants. The primary distinction is that the latter has a larger percentage of minerals like limestone, which is a significant part of crustacean waste (Zamani, 2010). Proteins and lipids are typically removed from chitin using 5% NaOH in the first step, and the dissolved mineral—which dissolves in acid—is removed using 30% HCl (Zamani, 2010). Chitin is the insoluble fraction that is left over following these processes. In order to extract chitosan from shells, carbonate is first dissolved or removed using 5% HCl or EDTA. Next, the proteins and lipid components are removed using 40% caustic soda at 110 °C while chitin is concurrently deacetylated to produce chitosan. Typically, chitin makes up 14–27% of the dry weight of shells; of that, 60–80% can be transformed into chitosan (Senel and McClure, 2004).

Enzymatic steps

Enzymatic hydrolysis with chitosanolytic enzymes particularly chitosanase have been another promising path and bio-technical input in chitosan production and processing from chitin (Yeul and Rayalu, 2013). Enzymes are known important bio-catalysts with specific affinity to their substrate(s); their presence in a reaction mixture speeds up a chemical reaction with less energy (enthalpy) inputs by their ability to reduce the barrier activation energy of every reaction path (Korma *et al.*, 2018). Better resolute chitosan from lignocellulosic material are produced with the presence of lignolytic enzymes such as chitosanase, arrays of peroxidases (laccase, Manganese peroxidases), pectinases, xylanase (Korma *et al.*, 2018).

Fig. 2 Different extraction pathways of chitosan from different sources (Korma *et al.*, 2018).

Fig. 3 industrial method of chitosan production from shells of sea animals using chemical means (Korma *et al.*, 2018).

General properties of Chitosan

Chitosan is a non-toxic biodegradable biopolymer with high molecular weight and similarity to cellulose (Korma *et al.*, 2018). Increasingly demand on chitosan commercially as suitable resource material due to their excellent properties including biocompatibility, biodegradability, adsorption, and ability to form films, and to chelate metal ions in waste water composites (Trombotto *et al.*, 2008). The following properties are of peculiarity to chitosans, they include:

Degree of Deacetylation

Deacetylation which is the last bioprocessing step in chitosan production from chitinous materials includes cutting the acetyl groups (COCH₃) off the chitin molecular chain, leaving behind chitosan, which is chemically active and has a highly reactive amino group (NH₂) (Akila, 2014). Because it influences the physicochemical properties of chitosan and, consequently, defines its acceptable uses, the degree of deacetylation (DD) is a crucial attribute of chitosan (Korma *et al.*, 2018).

Deacetylation largely affects the persistent (biodegradability) and immunological potential of chitosans. Chitosan's degree of deacetylation varies from 56% to 99%, with an average of 80%, contingent upon the type of crustacean and the techniques used during preparation. Chitosan is the term used to refer to chitin that has been deacetylated to a degree of 75% or above (Kasaai, 2009). The degree of chitosan deacetylation can be determined using a variety of techniques, according to reports. The ninhydrin test, hydrogen bromide titrimetry, nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, near-infrared spectroscopy, linear potentiometric titration, and first derivative UV spectrophotometry were among them (Stephenie, 2008)

Molecular weight

Chitosan are generally characterized with larger atomic mass and thus reflective in weight. Depending on its chemical constituents, the molar mass of the compound is a reflection of the sourced based materials contents and the modalities of production from the source samples (Korma *et al.*, 2018). Molecular weight of native chitin is usually larger than one million Daltons while commercial chitosan molecular weight range of 100,000 – 1,200,000 Daltons depending on the process and grades (levels) of the product (Kasaai, 2009).

Certain physical processes have been reported to affect the molecular weight of chitosans; at high temperature, dissolved oxygen and shear stress can cause degradation of chitosan. Also, maximal depolymerization of chitosan caused by utilization of high temperature or concentrated acids such as hydrochloric acid, acetic acid and sulphuric acid results in degradation of chitosan molecular structure with overall effects on the molecular weight (Akila, 2014). The molecular weight of chitosan can be determined using various analytical tools such as chromatography, light scattering, and viscometry (Wu *et al.*, 2005).

Viscosity

In order to determine the molecular weight of chitosan and determine its potential commercial applications in intricate biological systems, viscosity is a crucial physical element (Kim *et al.*, 2011). Comparing higher molecular weight chitosans to lower viscosity chitosans, which provide easier application, the former

frequently produce highly viscous solutions, which may not be ideal for industrial handling. The degree of deacetylation, molecular weight, solution concentration, ionic strength, pH, and temperature are some of the processing variables that have an impact on the synthesis of chitosan and its characteristics. As the demineralization period increases, chitosan's viscosity reduces (Korma *et al.*, 2018). It also rises when the degree of deacetylation and chitosan concentration rise, but falls when pH and temperature fall. (Kim *et al.*, 2011). It also rises when the degree of deacetylation and chitosan concentration rise, but falls when pH and temperature fall. There is a reputation for chitosan's ability to improve complexation. The biopolymer with a high degree of deacetylation exhibits a higher formulated chitosan (Kim *et al.*, 2011).

Solubility

Chitin, an acetylated While chitosan is easily soluble in diluted acidic solutions below pH6.0, it is insoluble in the majority of non-polar solvents (organic solvents). Chitosan is dissolved using organic acids including lactic, formic, and acetic acids as a solvent (Korma *et al.*, 2018). The standard solution that is most frequently used is 1% acetic acid solution. Chitosan is insoluble in phosphoric and sulfuric acids but soluble in 1% hydrochloric acid. Chitosan's solubility in inorganic acids is somewhat restricted (Akila, 2014). Concentrated acetic acid solutions at high temperature can cause depolymerization of chitosan. Chitosan's solubilization stability declines at neutral pH. Higher pH values tend to cause precipitation or gelation, with the chitosan solution forming poly-hydrocolloid and gelling as a result. To impart the appropriate functionality, the concentration ratio of acid to chitosan is crucial.

Chitosan continues to act as a viscosifier, keeping the solution smooth even at concentrations of up to 50% organic solvent. Physical parameters that are known to affect the solubility of chitosan include temperature and duration of deacetylation, alkali concentration (NaOH), ratio of chitin to alkali solution, particle size, and previous treatments used to isolate chitin (Abdelaziz, 2012). However, the degree of deacetylation controls solubility; to obtain the necessary solubilization, deacetylation is expected to need to be at least 85% complete. The acid-soluble chitosans with >95% solubility in 1% acetic acid at a 0.5% concentration may be prepared by treatment of the original chitin with 45% NaOH for 10-30 min (Akila, 2014).

Antimicrobial Properties

Antimicrobial activity of chitosan have revealed in the ability of the biopolymer in inhibiting the growth of bacteria (bacterostatic) and other adjoining pathogens (Kim *et al.*, 2011). The type of invasive pathogen and the molecular weight of chitosan determine its antibacterial capabilities. With the exception of *Lactobacillus* sp. strains, chitosan with 470 KDa is the most efficient against gram-positive bacteria; chitosan with 1,106 KDa, on the other hand, is effective against gram-negative bacteria (Knorr, 1982). In the presence of 0.1% chitosan, gram-positive bacteria (*Bacillus megaterium*, *B. cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *L. brevis*, and *L. bulgaris*) generally exhibited stronger bactericidal effects than gram-negative bacteria (*fluorescens*, *Salmonella typhimu parahaemolyticus*) (Almenar *et al.*, 2009).

N-carboxybutyl chitosan a derivative of chitosan during chitosan modification showed bacteriostatic and bactericidal activities on 298 different pathogenic microorganisms upon invivo

antimicrobial sensitivity tests carried out and they were marked morphological alterations in treated microorganisms when examined by electron microscopy (Korma *et al.*, 2018). Conversely, growth inhibition and attenuation of moulds and yeasts depend on chitosan concentration, pH, and temperature (Korma *et al.*, 2018). Both internal and external factors can affect chitosan's antimicrobial activity. These include the kind of chitosan (plainor derivative, for example), the degree of polymerization, the host's nutrient composition, the chemical and/or nutrient composition of the substrate, and environmental factors like substrate water activity (Akila, 2014). It has been demonstrated that chitosan coating greatly slows down fruit deterioration of vegetable and fruit decay at various temperatures (Rout, 2001).

Conclusion

Exceptional properties of the amine charged polymer has enlisted it as a promising biological polymer for present and future biotechnological applications. However there limited information as regards to the benefit of the compound in the agricultural sector. Owing to its physicochemical attributes it can pave way(s) for next generational biofertilizer.

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Ethical Delarations

The authors have disclosed no ethical concerns that might surface following the release of this work.

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